

Original article

Women's perspective on utilisation, and quality of basic emergency obstetrics and newborn care services in urban and rural communities of Kaduna State, Nigeria. a qualitative study.

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Abstract

Background: Emergency obstetric and newborn care (EmONC) reduces maternal and neonatal mortality, yet Nigeria faces high maternal and neonatal death rates. Despite improvements to PHCs in Kaduna State providing basic EmONC (BEmONC) services, utilisation and quality remain poor. **Objectives:** To assess and compare women's perspectives on BEmONC service utilisation and quality in urban and rural Kaduna. **Materials and Methods:** A qualitative study was conducted, using 12 FGDs involving 96 mothers of children under five, purposively selected from urban and rural communities. Mothers were stratified by age (<35 years and ≥35 years) and history of BEmONC service utilisation. FGDs were conducted using a validated discussion guide, audio-recorded, transcribed, and thematically analysed manually. **Results:** Mean ages were 32 ± 4 years (urban) and 30 ± 3 years (rural). Overall, 39.6% had secondary education and 54.2% were employed (urban); while 41.6% had primary education and 60.4% were unemployed (rural). Both groups recognized obstetric complications such as prolonged labour, convulsions, and postpartum haemorrhage. Urban women reported better access to emergency services, while rural women faced drug shortages and referral delays. Quality determinants included trained staff, essential drugs, and clean facilities. Barriers to utilisation included cost, transportation, and poor provider attitudes. Urban women perceived better quality due to improved infrastructure; rural women cited limited hours and lack of ambulances. **Conclusion:** Despite good awareness of obstetric complications, gaps persist in utilisation and perceived quality of BEmONC services—especially in rural Kaduna. Improving drug availability, providing emergency transport, increasing staff coverage, and mitigating financial barriers are essential interventions to improve maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Key Words: Basic Emergency Obstetric and Newborn Care, Focus Group Discussion, Quality, Rural, Utilisation, Urban

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Introduction

The provision of emergency obstetric and newborn care (EmONC) services has significantly reduced maternal and neonatal mortality in developed countries.¹ However, health systems in many developing nations continue to face challenges in delivering these critical services.¹ Globally, approximately 15% of pregnancies are complicated by life-threatening conditions, often requiring timely and skilled interventions.² In response, international health bodies introduced EmONC as a structured framework for delivering evidence-based maternal and neonatal care, especially in low-resource settings.^{2,3}

Despite global targets under the Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG 3) to reduce the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) to less than 70 per 100,000 live births, developing countries still bear the biggest brunt of preventable maternal and newborn deaths.^{4,5,6} In 2022, the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) and neonatal mortality rate in Nigeria are about 512 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births

and 35 deaths per 1,000 live births, respectively. Also, there is a lifetime risk of one in every 22 women dying as a result of pregnancy, delivery, postpartum, or post-abortion complications. The MMR is majorly due to preventable obstetrics complications.^{7, 8, 9} In Kaduna State, the situation is even more alarming, with a maternal mortality ratio of 1,025 per 100,000 live births. The neonatal mortality rate was 47 per 1,000 live births in 2021.¹⁰ Evidence shows that appropriate EmONC services could prevent up to 60% of maternal and 85% of intrapartum-related deaths. However, gaps in availability, utilisation, and quality persist—especially between urban and rural areas.^{8,9} Rural primary healthcare centres (PHCs), which serve as the primary point of care (80.9%) for many pregnant women, often lack the capacity to manage obstetric emergencies effectively.¹¹

This study aims to assess and compare women's perspectives on the utilisation, and quality of basic emergency obstetric and newborn care (BEmONC) services in urban and rural communities in Kaduna State. The findings will help identify gaps and inform targeted policy interventions to improve maternal and newborn outcomes across different geographic settings.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in 2023 in Kaduna State, located in the northwest geopolitical zone of Nigeria. population of 9.48 million people based on projection from the 2006 population census to the year 2023.^{12, 13} About 49% of the population are females. Of which 51% are between the ages of 15 and 64 years, and 55% of the population are rural dwellers.¹⁰ The state has a maternal mortality ratio of 1,025 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births, and the neonatal mortality rate was 47 per 1,000 live births.¹⁰ The state has 1,068 functional primary health care facilities that provide health care services even in the most remote areas of the state. In each of the 255 political wards, 1 focal PHC was renovated and equipped in 2017 to offer at least BEmONC.¹⁴

The study was a qualitative cross-sectional study design. Data collection was conducted among mothers of children under the age of 5 years. Mothers who were not permanent residents of the selected communities were excluded from the study.

A multistage sampling technique was used. From each of the three senatorial districts (Kaduna North and Kaduna South are made up of eight local government areas (LGAs) each, while Kaduna Central is made up of seven), one LGA was selected

through simple random sampling by balloting, which was made up of three local government areas selected (Kudan, Chikun, and Jema'a LGAs). The map of Kaduna State showing Senatorial Districts and LGAs is shown in Figure 1. Through simple random sampling by balloting, one ward was selected from each of the three selected LGAs, which made up a total of three wards. A settlement is a neighbourhood with people living within it mostly having similar characteristics. Nigeria's Geo-Referenced Infrastructure and Demographic Data for Development (GRID³) has classified the settlements into urban and rural.¹⁵ A list of these settlements and their classification in the selected wards was obtained from the Kaduna State Bureau of Statistics.¹⁶ The list was stratified into urban and rural, and two settlements were selected from each stratum, which made a total of four settlements from each ward and a total of 12 settlements (six urban and six rural) across the selected three wards. Twelve focus group discussions (FGDs) were conducted, four in each of the three selected local government areas. Overall, six FGDs were conducted in urban settlements, of which three FGDs were among women who had utilised the BEmONC services and three among women who had not utilised the services. Also, six FGDs were conducted in rural settlements, of which three FGDs were among women who had utilised the BEmONC services and three among women who had not utilised the services.

Eight eligible women were selected per FGD group, giving a total of 96 women. The women were purposively selected based on their willingness to participate and give their perspectives. The FGD groups constituted such homogenous groups of women less than 35 years of age who had utilised BEmONC services; women less than 35 years of age who had not utilised BEmONC services; women aged 35 years and above who had utilised BEmONC services; and women aged 35 years and above who had not utilised BEmONC services within the urban and rural settlements. An FGD guide was adapted from the "field-friendly guide to integrate Emergency Obstetric Care in humanitarian programs".¹⁷ The FGD sessions were audio-recorded to enable proper and full documentation of each woman's contribution. Each of the discussions lasted for about one hour and was conducted in places that were convenient and provided privacy and confidentiality to the women. Frequency of socio-demographics was reported with their percentages. Mean ages were reported with their standard deviations, and data was presented in a table. The audio recordings and field

notes were transcribed in Hausa language and then translated into English language. Content analysis along thematic lines was done, and the findings were reported in narrative form.

Figure 1: Map of Kaduna State Showing Senatorial Districts and Local Government Areas. Source: <https://www.kadrima.com.ng/registration-centers/>.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital Zaria (ABUTHZ/HREC/H41/2022). Permission was sought from the Kaduna State Primary Health Care Development Agency and community leaders of the communities selected. Verbal informed consent was obtained from each woman before the commencement of FGDs.

Results

Socio-demographic Characteristics of Women

There were 96 women who participated in the FGDs. The mean age of the women was 32 ± 4 years for urban communities and 30 ± 3 years for rural. Overall, 39.6% of women had secondary education in urban communities, and 41.6% had primary education in rural communities. About 54.2% were employed in urban communities, and 60.4% were unemployed in rural. Other sociodemographic results are shown in table 1.

The themes used for the FGD were the utilisation of BEMONC services, women’s perspective of the quality of BEMONC services, women’s perspective of determinants of utilisation of BEMONC services, and women’s perspective of determinants of the quality of BEMONC services.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Urban and Rural Women in Focus Group Discussions in Kaduna State

Socio-demographics	Urban(n=48)				Rural(n=48)			
	Utilised (n=24)		Not Utilise (n=24)		Utilised (n=24)		Not Utilise (n=24)	
	<35yrs f (%)	≥35yrs f (%)	<35yrs f (%)	≥35yrs f (%)	<35yrs f (%)	≥35yrs f (%)	<35yrs f (%)	≥35yrs f (%)
Marital status								
Married	14(87.5)	7(87.5)	13(81.3)	8(100.0)	15(93.8)	8(100.0)	16(100.0)	8(100.0)
Unmarried	2(12.5)	1(12.5)	3(18.7)	-	1(6.2)	-	-	-
Religion								
Islam	8(50.0)	5(62.5)	9(56.3)	5(62.5)	10(62.5)	7(87.5)	11(68.8)	5(62.5)
Christianity	8(50.0)	3(37.5)	7(43.7)	3(37.5)	6(37.5)	1(12.5)	5(32.2)	3(37.5)
Ethnicity								
Hausa	9(56.3)	3(37.5)	12(75.0)	4(50.0)	13(81.3)	5(62.5)	8(50.0)	5(62.5)
Igbo	1(6.2)	1(12.5)	-	-	1(6.2)	1(12.5)	2(12.5)	-
Yoruba	2(12.5)	1(12.5)	1(6.3)	2(25.0)	-	-	-	-
Others	4(25.0)	3(37.5)	3(18.7)	2(25.0)	2(12.5)	2(25.0)	6(37.5)	3(37.5)
Employment								
Employed	10(62.5)	5(62.5)	7(43.7)	4(50.0)	5(31.3)	6(75.0)	6(37.5)	2(25.0)
Unemployed	6(37.5)	3(37.5)	9(56.3)	4(50.0)	11(68.7)	2(25.0)	10(62.5)	6(75.0)
Education								
None	3(18.8)	2(25.0)	3(18.8)	3(37.5)	4(25.0)	2(25.0)	5(31.3)	4(50.0)
Primary	2(12.4)	1(12.5)	4(25.0)	3(37.5)	6(37.5)	5(62.5)	7(43.7)	2(25.0)
Secondary	8(50.0)	3(37.5)	7(43.7)	1(12.5)	5(31.3)	1(12.5)	3(18.8)	2(25.0)
Tertiary	3(18.8)	2(25.0)	2(12.5)	1(12.5)	1(6.2)	-	1(6.2)	-

Women's Perspective on Utilisation of BEmONC Services

The women who had utilised BEmONC services revealed that women in urban communities while pregnant or delivery develop such complications as prolonged labour, as one of the women said, "You know that the situation of labour differs as some have shorter labour while some have to labour for a longer period", high blood pressure during pregnancy, convulsions, blood loss (one of the women said, "After delivery women usually experience severe loss of blood"); headache, leg swelling, severe abdominal pain after delivery; the placenta may remain in the uterus; and the baby may not start breathing. These findings were similar to the ones that rural women who had utilised the delivery services revealed. Even women who did not utilise the BEmONC services mentioned such complications during the FGDs with both urban and rural women.

When they were asked about the different treatments given to women when they developed the complications, urban women who had utilised BEmONC services mentioned injections for convulsions and high blood pressure, injections for prolonged labour (oxytocin), injections to limit bleeding, resuscitation of a child who does not start breathing after delivery, and manual removal of the placenta, as one of the women said, "Someone will give birth and the placenta will follow, but for someone it will take time before the placenta will come out; for some, they will suffer, and at the end they will have to remove it manually." For complications that the PHCs could not treat, they usually refer to either general or tertiary hospitals. Similar to rural women who had utilised the services but did not mention removal of the placenta and injection to limit bleeding, as one woman said, "The drugs here are sometimes not available". However, women who did not utilise these services in both urban and rural settlements said they do not know what treatments were given in the hospital.

Women's Perspective on Quality of BEmONC Services

When the urban women were asked about the quality of the delivery services provided by the health facilities in their communities, they revealed that there were beds for deliveries, few trained staff, and they received poor care from the staff; there was erratic availability of required drugs, a clean environment, and they sometimes received encouragement and counselling and care of the newborn. One of the respondents said, "Alhamdulillah, in the provision of services, at least there is progress." And another said "akwai daidai

gwargwado," referring to the quality being average. These findings were similar to that of rural women but did mention that staff did not work for 24 hours a day. And there were no ambulances for referral in all the PHCs; one woman said, "Truly there is no vehicle."

Women's Perspective of Determinants of Utilisation of BEmONC Services

When the urban women were asked of factors that influence the extent to which the women utilise delivery services, some mentioned facilitators, as when a woman is sick (developed a danger sign) or in labour, literacy level facilitates going to the hospital, age increases wisdom and decision-making, as one woman said, "Yes, age can make you know what is affecting you, and it also increases your wisdom to know what to do," and high income. While the limiting factors were lack of transportation ("and you know transportation is expensive now, right," one woman said), lack of money, cost of services, long waiting time (as one woman said, "Truly it is part of the reasons why some women will not want to come to the hospital because if they come and they are not attended to on time, next time if they know there is a queue, they will not come"), and regular referral and decision of spouse. These findings were similar to that of rural women.

Women's Perspective of Determinants of Quality of BEmONC Services

When the urban women were asked of the factors that influence the quality of the delivery services, responses were prompt treatment in terms of emergency, available essential drugs, as a woman said, "They don't talk to us harshly; we are enjoying their work, except for the problem of lack of drugs and working tools," good environment, trained staff availability, as one woman said, "If there are many workers, we will not be discouraged from coming here," and availability of transport for referral. In addition to the aforementioned, rural women added that short waiting times and good beds increase the quality of BEmONC services.

Discussion

On the utilisation of BEmONC services, most of the urban and rural women, among both BEmONC utilisers and non-utilisers were able to mention some complications that a woman can develop while pregnant or during delivery. They mentioned that a woman can develop such complications as prolonged labour, high blood pressure during pregnancy, convulsions, blood loss, headache, leg swelling, severe abdominal pain after delivery, the

placenta may remain in the uterus, and the baby may not start breathing. These complications are synonymous with obstetrics danger signs. These findings were similar to a study from Kano¹⁸ and Jigawa¹⁹ States, which found that the majority of the women were able to identify obstetric danger signs. However, some studies from Northern Nigeria²⁰ and Ethiopia²¹ found poor knowledge of pregnancy or delivery-related complication identification among women.

Although most women in both urban and rural areas who were non-utilisers, were able to identify obstetric complications, that did not lead to the use of Basic Emergency Obstetric and Newborn Care (BEmONC) services. Similar findings in other studies showed that awareness of danger signs alone does not translate into healthcare-seeking behaviour when there is persistence of such structural barriers as distance, costs, and poor facility readiness.²²⁻²⁴ However, among users, recognition of complications sets the first step towards seeking BEmONC services, which is consistent with some findings that good knowledge of pregnancy and delivery danger signs enhances timely healthcare-seeking behaviour.^{25,26}

The range of treatments described by urban utilisers compared to rural utilisers, agrees with evidence of greater service readiness and drug availability in urban PHCs.^{27,28} Frequent stock-outs of such essential drugs as oxytocin and magnesium sulfate in rural PHCs have been associated with reduced utilisation and increased bypassing of lower-level care.^{29,30} Furthermore, long referral distances to secondary or tertiary facilities further discourage healthcare-seeking behaviour, contributing to poor maternal health outcomes.^{24,31} These will affect the indicators of utilisation of BEmONC services by decreasing the proportion of births taking place in BEmONC facilities and the met needs for BEmONC, thereby falling short of the required minimum standard by WHO.³¹ Thus, the need to strengthen PHC capacity, ensure consistent drug supply, and improve referral systems to translate knowledge into effective BEmONC service utilisation.

The urban women's perspective on the quality of BEmONC services provided by the health facilities in their communities revealed that there were beds for deliveries, few trained staff, poor care from the staff, erratic availability of required drugs, a clean environment, encouragement and counselling sometimes, and care of the newborn. These findings were similar to that of rural women but did mention that staff did not work for 24 hours a day.

This study found that there were no ambulances for referrals in all the PHCs, which is similar to a study carried out in Northwest Nigeria.¹⁹ The poor perceived quality will lead to poor women's satisfaction with the services. The poor perceived quality of BEmONC services will significantly contribute to indicators of quality of BEmONC services, such as case fatality rate due to direct obstetric causes and intrapartum and very early neonatal death rate.³²

From the urban women's perspective on determinants of utilisation of BEmONC services, they mentioned facilitators of utilisation as when a woman is sick (developed a danger sign), in labour, literacy level facilitates going to hospital, age increases wisdom and decision making, and high income. While the limiting factors were lack of transportation, lack of money, cost of services, and long waiting time, and regular referral and decision of spouse. These findings were similar to that of rural women. The absence of means of referrals and the referrals to other facilities will invariably increase the cost of transportation and care for services, which the women most of the time cannot afford. These will increase financial burden and out-of-pocket expenditure which will invariably decrease the utilisation of BEmONC services, this will in turn affect the demand generation for maternal health services.¹⁹

Finally, the women's perspective on determinants of quality of BEmONC services, mentioned the factors that influences the quality of the delivery services as prompt treatment in terms of emergency, available essential drugs, good environment, trained staff availability, and availability of transport for referral. In addition to the aforementioned, rural women added short waiting time and good beds increases the quality of BEmONC services.

These findings were similar to that of a study in North-West Nigeria¹⁹ and Ethiopia³³ where they identified such factors as inadequate skill mix of maternity health personnel, poor referral processes, lack of reliable communication systems and poor transport systems. Where these factors adversely affect the quality of BEmONC services, they will negatively affect women's patronage to seek for the services when they develop complications of delivery, thereby, leading to poor maternal and child health outcomes.

However, the study has few limitations. The study's qualitative design limits the generalizability of its findings. Information bias may have occurred, as some participants might have withheld accurate responses in the group setting. However, this risk

was reduced by stratifying participants by age and BEmONC service utilisation status. Notwithstanding, the study findings have implications for policy and practice. The limiting factors for service utilisation and poor quality, especially in rural PHCs, indicate a need for targeted interventions while reinforcing the facilitatory factors.

Conclusion

Women in urban and rural Kaduna recognized complications like prolonged labour, convulsions, and bleeding. Urban utilisers of BEmONC services reported receiving treatments such as oxytocin, convulsion management, and neonatal resuscitation, while rural utilisers cited drug shortages and fewer services. Barriers to utilisation included cost, poor transport, long waiting times, and lack of decision-making power. Utilisation was directly influenced by literacy, income, and awareness of danger signs. Both groups noted quality factors like clean facilities, trained staff, and emergency response, though rural areas lacked ambulances and 24-hour staff coverage. Kaduna State government should ensure consistent supply of essential drugs and emergency equipment in rural PHCs and strengthen referral systems with 24-hour ambulance services and trained personnel. The Kaduna State Government should strengthen women empowerment programmes and increase health education campaigns to address the issues of illiteracy, lack of decision-making power, and poor income among women.

Authors' Contribution

ZM: Conceptualised and designed the study, conducted data collection, performed data analysis, interpreted results, drafted the original manuscript, revised the manuscript, and approved the final version. MSI: Conceptualised and designed the study, contributed to manuscript drafting and revision, and approved the final version. IM: Contributed manuscript drafting and revision and approved the final version. AIS: Contributed manuscript drafting and revision and approved the final version. UI: Contributed manuscript drafting and revision and approved the final version. NM: Contributed manuscript drafting and revision and approved the final version.

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